

Functional Evaluation of Hyaluronic Acid and Collagen Infiltration in Gonarthrosis II in a Secondlevel Hospital

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ABSTRACT

Background: Knee osteoarthritis is a leading cause of pain and disability, with increasing incidence associated with aging and obesity. Intra-articular therapies such as collagen and hyaluronic acid injections have emerged as valuable alternatives for symptom relief and functional improvement in patients with gonarthrosis.

Objective: To evaluate functional outcomes following intra-articular infiltration with hyaluronic acid and collagen in patients with grade II gonarthrosis treated at the General Regional Hospital of Orizaba.

Methods: A descriptive, prospective, and analytical study was conducted in 120 patients diagnosed with grade II gonarthrosis who received intra-articular infiltration with either HA or collagen. Functional assessment was performed using the validated Spanish version of the WOMAC scale (Cronbach's alpha 0.92). Patients were followed for six weeks. Data analysis was conducted with SPSS v25, using measures of central tendency and dispersion, frequency distribution, Pearson's chi-square test, and Student's *t-test* for independent variables. A *p* value < 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

Results: Both treatment groups demonstrated improvement in functional scores at six weeks. Comparative analysis showed functional benefits in both therapies, with differential patterns of improvement between and collagen.

Conclusions: Intra-articular infiltration with hyaluronic acid and collagen provides functional improvement in patients with grade II gonarthrosis. These therapies represent effective non-surgical management options, supporting their clinical utility in early-stage.

KEYWORDS: hyaluronic acid infiltration, collagen infiltration, gonarthrosis, functionality, clinical response, WOMAC (Spanish).

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INTRODUCTION

Knee osteoarthritis is one of the leading causes of pain, functional limitations, and disability in adults worldwide. Its prevalence increases significantly with age, particularly in individuals with obesity, altered biomechanical factors, or a history of joint injuries. In Mexico, the estimated prevalence is 10.5%, with a higher incidence in women, representing a

growing challenge for health services due to the aging population and the increasing burden of associated chronic diseases.

The management of osteoarthritis requires a comprehensive approach that combines non-pharmacological and pharmacological interventions, and, in advanced cases, surgical procedures. In patients with early or moderate

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gonarthrosis, conservative therapies remain the first line of treatment, emphasizing patient education, therapeutic exercise, weight loss, and the use of analgesics or anti-inflammatories. However, the clinical response to these measures can be limited, which has driven the search for intra-articular therapeutic alternatives that improve pain and joint function.

Among the available options, hyaluronic acid infiltration has been widely used due to its role as a natural component of synovial fluid, which acts as a lubricant, shock absorber, and inflammatory modulator. Meanwhile, polymerized collagen has emerged as an alternative with potential chondroprotective and regenerative effects, supported by studies suggesting its ability to promote cartilage repair and improve symptoms in patients with gonarthrosis.

Although several studies have evaluated the individual efficacy of these therapies, comparative evidence between hyaluronic acid and collagen remains limited, especially in the Mexican population with grade II gonarthrosis. Having local data is essential to guide therapeutic choices based on objective clinical outcomes.

In this context, the present study aims to analyze the functional response following intra-articular infiltration with hyaluronic acid and collagen in patients with grade II gonarthrosis treated at a secondary-level hospital, using the WOMAC index as a validated measurement tool for clinical evaluation.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

This study adhered to international ethical standards, institutional guidelines, and the provisions of the General Health Law regarding scientific experimentation in human subjects, specifically Articles 13, 16, and 20, and the 1964 Declaration of Helsinki, which states that the primary purpose of medical research involving human subjects is to understand the causes, evolution, and effects of diseases and to improve preventive, diagnostic, and therapeutic interventions.

Design

This descriptive, prospective, and analytical study was conducted between April and October 2025 at Regional General Hospital No. 1 in Orizaba, Veracruz.

Population and Sample

One hundred and twenty patients with a clinical and radiographic diagnosis gonarthrosis II were included. The sample was non-probabilistic and based on convenience sampling, and consisted of:

- Group A: 60 patients who received hyaluronic acid injections.
- Group B: 60 patients infiltrated with collagen.

Inclusion criteria:

- Age ≥ 30 years.
- Diagnosis of gonarthrosis II.
- Complete medical record.

- Acceptance of infiltration.

Exclusion criteria:

- Degenerative ligamentous or meniscal pathology.
- Previous surgical treatment.
- Lack of follow-up at 6 weeks.

Measurement Instrument

The WOMAC scale (Spanish validated version; Cronbach's alpha 0.92) was used to assess pain, stiffness, and physical function. Scores were converted to a 0–96 scale (higher score = worse functionality).

Functional classification:

- Good: 1–30
- Fair: 31–60
- Poor: 61–96

Procedure

1. During the evaluation of each patient with grade II gonarthrosis, they were enrolled and assessed using the WOMAC (Western Ontario and McMaster Universities Osteoarthritis Index) functional scale, categorized prior to infiltration.
2. Intra-articular infiltration of hyaluronic acid or collagen was administered to the assigned group of 120 patients.
3. Re-evaluation was performed at 6 weeks using the WOMAC (Western Ontario and McMaster Universities Osteoarthritis Index) functional scale, categorizing each patient.

Statistical Analysis

SPSS v25 was used. The following tests were applied:

- Pearson's chi-squared test for categorical variables.
- $p < 0.05$ considered statistically significant.

RESULTS

In this study, entitled " Functional evaluation of hyaluronic acid and collagen infiltration in gonarthrosis II in a second-level hospital " the following results were obtained from the sample of 120 patients with grade II gonarthrosis: 82 were women (68.3%) and 38 were men (31.7%). (See Table 1)

Table 1. Sex in Patients with Grade II Gonarthrosis

	Frecuencia	Porcentaje
Male	38	31.7
Female	82	68.3
Total	120	100

The predominance of sex in patients with grade II gonarthrosis was female with 82 patients (68.3%), $n=120$. According to age group, there were 2 patients between 31 and 40 years old (1.6%) with grade II gonarthrosis, followed by 8 patients (6.7%) between 41 and 50 years old, 25 (20.8%)

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between 51 and 60 years old, 54 (45%) between 61 and 70 years old, 26 (21.7%) between 71 and 80 years old, and 5 (4.2%) over 81 years old, as shown in Table 2.

Table 2. Age of patients with grade II gonarthrosis

Grupo de edad	Frecuencia	Porcentaje
31-40	2	1.6
41-50	8	6.7
51-60	25	20.8
61-70	54	45
71-80	26	21.7
≥81	5	4.2
Total	120	100

Age groups in patients with grade II gonarthrosis showed a predominance of the 6170 age group with 54 patients (45) n=120.

The study included 120 patients with grade II gonarthrosis. The WOMAC scale, which assesses knee function, was applied. Sixty patients underwent hyaluronic acid injections, yielding the following results: good function in 2 patients (3.3%), acceptable function in 32 patients (53.3%), and poor function in 26 patients (43.3%). (See Table 3)

Table 3. Knee function prior to hyaluronic acid injection

Functional	Frequency	Percentage
Good	2	3.3
Fair	32	53.3
Poor	26	43.3
Total	60	100

Acceptable functional capacity was the predominant finding, with 32 patients (53.3%) out of 60.

Of the 60 patients who underwent hyaluronic acid injections and were evaluated after 6 weeks using the WOMAC scale, the following results were obtained: good functionality in 38 patients (63.3%), acceptable functionality in 14 patients (23.3%), and poor functionality in 8 patients (13.4%). (See Table 4).

Table 4. Functional capacity at 6 weeks after hyaluronic acid injection

Functional	Frequency	Percentage
Good	38	63.3
Fair	14	23.3
Poor	8	13.4
Total	60	100

A predominance of good functional capacity is observed with 38 patients (63.3) n=60.

Of the 60 patients who entered the collagen infiltration protocol, the WOMAC scale was applied prior to infiltration. The following results were obtained: good functionality in 31 patients (51.6%), acceptable functionality in 24 patients (40%), and poor functionality in 5 patients (8.4%). (See Table 5)

Table 5. Functional capacity of the knee prior to collagen infiltration

Functional	Frequency	Percentage
Buena	31	51.6
Acceptable	24	40
Mala	5	8.4
Total	60	100

A predominance of acceptable functional capacity was observed in 31 patients (51.6%), n=60.

Of the 60 patients infiltrated with collagen and evaluated after 6 weeks using the WOMAC scale, the following results were obtained: good functionality in 50 patients (83.3%), acceptable functionality in 5 patients (8.3%), and poor functionality in 5 patients (8.3%). (See Table 6)

Table 6. Functional capacity of 60 patients after 6 weeks of collagen infiltration.

Functional	Frequency	Percentage
Good	50	83.3
Fair	5	8.3
Poor	5	8.3q
Total	60	100

A predominance of good functional capacity was observed in 50 patients (83.3%) (n=60).

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The association between hyaluronic acid or collagen application and knee function was assessed using the WOMAC questionnaire. Functionality with hyaluronic acid was found to be good in 38 patients (63.3%), acceptable in 14

Table 7 shows the application of hyaluronic acid and collagen treatments.

Treatment	Functional						p= 0.037
							Chi2=6.592
							gl=2
	Good		Fair		Poor		Total
	n	%	n	%	n	%	
Ácido hialurónico	38	63.3	14	23.3	8	13.3	60
Colágeno	50	83.3	5	8.3	5	8.3	60
							120

Collagen application predominated in 50 patients (83.3%) with good functionality. The association between variables yielded a Pearson chi-square result of 6.592, $df=2$, p -value=0.037, $n=120$.

DISCUSSION

The findings of this study demonstrate that both hyaluronic acid (HA) and collagen are effective interventions for the management of grade II gonarthrosis, achieving clinical improvements exceeding 60%. These results are closely related to those reported by In et al. (2025), who, in a multicenter setting in South Korea, found no significant differences between porcine atelocollagen and HA at 24 weeks (30). Similarly, the consistency in functional improvement observed in our HA group aligns with the experience of Gaitán and Sevilla (2024) in Peru, reaffirming that viscosupplementation is a solid pillar in secondary-level hospital treatment (31). However, our study highlights a statistical advantage of collagen in achieving "good" functionality (83.3% vs. 63.3%), suggesting that its role is not only palliative but potentially structural.

Despite the equivalence reported in global meta-analyses such as that by Pereira TV et al. (2022), which describes a modest but significant benefit of viscosupplementation compared to placebo (32), our research stands out by prioritizing functionality as a key indicator of success. This is the study's main strength: the use of objective variables such as stiffness and functional capacity, which provide high external validity by reflecting the patient's recovery of autonomy. By addressing the tissue through a dual action of lubrication and structural support, these therapies are positioned as safe alternatives that reduce pharmacological dependence.

patients (9.5%), and poor in 8 patients (13.3%). With collagen, function was good in 50 patients (83.3%), acceptable in 5 patients (8.3%), and poor in 5 patients (8.3%), with a p value of 0.037 and a Chi-square value of 6.592.

A relevant finding of this study was the baseline functional difference between treatment groups prior to infiltration. Patients in the hyaluronic acid group presented a higher proportion of poor baseline functionality (43.4%) compared to the collagen group (8.4%). This lack of baseline homogeneity should be considered when interpreting post-treatment functional outcomes, as greater initial functional impairment may limit the magnitude of clinical recovery. Previous comparative studies have shown that baseline functional status significantly influences therapeutic response following intra-articular injections. Despite this difference, both treatments demonstrated functional improvement, supporting their clinical usefulness in patients with grade II knee osteoarthritis this baseline difference represents a limitation of the study and should be considered when interpreting comparative outcomes..

However, the short follow-up period (6 weeks) must be recognized as a critical weakness. This time limitation prevents us from determining the durability of the therapeutic effect and the degradation kinetics of the compounds in the extracellular matrix. To address this, future research should consider the application of a single dose of high molecular weight hyaluronic acid. This technique would not only optimize patient adherence by reducing interventions but would also facilitate study designs with extended follow-up periods of up to 12 months, allowing for a more precise evaluation of the success rate in postponing joint replacement surgeries.

CONCLUSIONS: The null hypothesis is rejected, suggesting superior functional outcomes associated with collagen infiltration (83.3%) compared to hyaluronic acid (63.3%) in patients with grade II gonarthrosis ($p = 0.037$).

Both therapies are essential for improving quality of life and delaying disease progression. Timely intervention at the secondary care level not only restores patient autonomy but also represents a preventive cost-saving strategy for the healthcare system (HGRO) by deferring the need for total knee arthroplasty.

While hyaluronic acid fulfills a mechanical and lubricating function, collagen is emerging as an alternative with regenerative potential, offering comprehensive recovery based on the structural support of the joint.

It is imperative to integrate these protocols into comprehensive patient education programs. It is suggested that future studies explore single-dose protocols with longterm monitoring (12 months) to consolidate evidence on

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functional stability and the sustainability of the treatment over time.

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